

27 **ABSTRACT**

28 The adsorptive dechlorination of a pyrolysis oil coming from real plastic waste was investigated
29 using different Na-zeolites (4A, 13X, and Y) as adsorbents. The dechlorination experiments were
30 performed in a fixed bed trap under inert atmosphere operating at moderate temperatures (<
31 180 °C). The dechlorination efficiency of the adsorbents was significantly improved by
32 performing a dehydration pre-treatment due to the removal of water molecules physisorbed on
33 the zeolite surface. Among the zeolitic materials tested, 13X zeolite showed the best
34 dechlorination efficiency, which was related to its high content of Lewis acid sites (attributed to
35 the presence of Na⁺ cations ionically interacting with the zeolite framework), acting as
36 chemisorption sites, as well as the high accessibility of the FAU-zeolitic topology to the Cl-
37 containing compounds. For that sample, a detailed study of the adsorption temperature (from
38 30 to 180 °C) and time on stream (1-6 h) was further carried out. The maximum chlorine removal
39 efficiency was achieved, reducing the chlorine content of the pyrolysis oil from 421 to 45 ppm,
40 at temperatures of about 150–180 °C. Interestingly, under these conditions, thermal or catalytic
41 cracking effects of the zeolite on the feedstock were not observed. However, the study of the
42 time on stream showed that, after 3 h, the chlorine removal efficiency of the zeolite started to
43 decrease. Thus, different regeneration treatments were evaluated proving that, after a
44 combustion at 600 °C, the zeolite recovered its initial dechlorination efficiency. This research
45 reveals the potential of the adsorptive dechlorination process with Na-zeolites to reduce the
46 chlorine content in plastic pyrolysis oils under mild operating conditions.

47

48

49

50

51

52

53

54

55 Keywords: Zeolites; chlorine; plastic pyrolysis oils; dechlorination; adsorption

56 1. INTRODUCTION

57 The growing volume of discarded plastic waste is one of the most critical environmental and
58 health global concerns. [1,2] Traditional methods for plastics management, such as landfilling or
59 incineration, have serious drawbacks due to the low degradability of plastics and/or the
60 emission of harmful compounds (heavy metals, dioxins, furans, acid gases, and particles) into
61 the atmosphere during their combustion. [2,3] Despite these issues, in 2020, most discarded
62 plastics in the European Union (EU) (ca. 42 wt%) were incinerated as part of municipal solid
63 waste (MSW) while ca. 23 wt% was still sent to landfill. [4] To overcome this situation, the EU
64 has adopted the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy, aimed at making all plastic
65 packaging on the EU market recyclable by 2030 and minimizing the consumption of single-use
66 plastics. [5,6] In this context, effective reuse and recycling technologies are urgently needed to
67 reintegrate plastic waste into the production cycle.

68 Mechanical recycling is a simple and cost-effective approach but is not suitable for the
69 reprocessing of composite or multilayer plastics such as those used for food packaging. In
70 addition, the resultant recycled materials often show poor technical properties, hindering their
71 use in further applications. [7] On the other hand, chemical recycling comprises a group of
72 alternative technologies, including depolymerization, gasification, and pyrolysis, which allow the
73 conversion of plastic residues into raw products for chemical and petrochemical industries. [8]
74 Among them, pyrolysis is one of the most promising options, leading to the production of a liquid
75 fraction (pyrolysis oil) that could be used as a precursor of valuable chemical products. This
76 process offers important advantages since it is carried out under an oxygen-free atmosphere,
77 avoiding the formation of toxic pollutants, such as dioxins. Moreover, it does not require any
78 feedstock segregation pre-treatment making it a suitable alternative for the processing of
79 heterogeneous or mixed plastic waste streams. [9,10]

80 Plastic pyrolysis has been widely studied in the last decades to valorize single polymers including
81 polypropylene (PP), low- and high-density polyethylene (LDPE and HDPE, respectively),
82 polystyrene (PS), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), etc. [11,12] The properties of pyrolysis oils
83 depend on the composition of the raw plastic and the process conditions (temperature,
84 presence of a catalyst, reactor type, etc.). Thus, previous studies have demonstrated that the
85 pyrolysis oils of polyolefinic polymers (polyethylene, PE, and polypropylene, PP) exhibit similar
86 characteristics to those of conventional fossil fuels. [13] However, a significant challenge arises
87 when dealing with real discarded plastics since they are usually comprised of mixed materials,
88 including other polymers such as polystyrene (PS), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and/or

89 halogenated polymers like polyvinyl chloride (PVC). In addition, they could contain diverse
90 heteroatoms (nitrogen, oxygen, halogens, and metals), coming from fillers, flame retardants,
91 pigments, and other additives, which hinders the large-scale implementation of plastic waste
92 pyrolysis. [14,15,16] One of the most important contaminants of pyrolysis oils coming from
93 MSW discarded plastics is chlorine, whose main source is PVC and other chlorinated polymers
94 (i.e. chlorinated polyethylene) used in the manufacture of food packaging, bottles, electrical
95 wires, etc. [17] During the pyrolysis process, chlorine can be released as hydrogen chloride (HCl)
96 or converted into chlorinated hydrocarbons, leading to severe corrosion or fouling issues as well
97 as to catalyst poisoning and deactivation. [18,19] Thus, Cl-containing compounds must be
98 removed from pyrolysis oils before being directly used as fuels or co-processed in conventional
99 refineries. [19,20]

100 The chlorine content of the plastic waste used as feedstock can be reduced by washing
101 pretreatments with hot water or alkali solutions. However, the resultant pyrolysis oil still
102 contains a significant amount of chlorine (> 150 ppm), requiring further treatments to achieve a
103 more suitable product. [21,22] Stepwise pyrolysis has been also widely applied for the
104 dechlorination of PVC-containing plastic mixtures. In this process, chlorine is firstly removed in
105 the form of HCl at low temperatures (240 – 340 °C) and subsequently captured in a NaOH
106 solution. [19,23] Then, at temperatures higher than 370 °C, the polymer chains are decomposed,
107 yielding the formation of different hydrocarbons. However, not all chlorine present in the
108 feedstock can be removed as HCl, a part of it remaining in the pyrolysis oil in the form of different
109 organochloride species. The dechlorination efficiency of the stepwise pyrolysis can be improved
110 by the addition of different adsorbents either mixed with the feedstock (in situ) or passing the
111 pyrolysis vapors in a separated bed (ex situ). [20] In this sense, different basic oxides and
112 carbonates, including CaCO₃, CaO, Ca(OH)₂, Na₂CO₃, as well as diverse iron oxides, have been
113 used as HCl adsorbents. [20,24-27] Moreover, the quality of the pyrolysis product can be further
114 improved by combining the stepwise dechlorination with the addition of a catalytic system, such
115 as La/MgO-based materials, Red Mud or ZSM-5 zeolite, which also have a significant impact in
116 the hydrocarbons distribution of the pyrolysis oil. [28,29,30] Catalytic hydrodechlorination is
117 another alternative for organic chlorine removal in plastic pyrolysis oils. However, this approach
118 requires high hydrogen pressures and the utilization of noble metal-based catalysts, which
119 reduces the cost-effectiveness of the process. [31] Therefore, it is essential to develop
120 complementary upgrading methods to reduce the organic chlorine content in plastic pyrolysis
121 oils. [32]

122 Alternatively, adsorptive dechlorination could be a simple and cost-effective technology for the
123 organic chlorine removal of hydrocarbon streams, as it does not require the use of expensive
124 reagents or severe operation conditions. This process typically is carried out by passing the
125 hydrocarbon stream through an adsorbent bed, where the organochlorinated compounds are
126 selectively retained. Different FAU-type zeolites have been investigated as adsorbents for
127 chlorine removal from crude oil fractions due to their high specific surface area, tunable
128 porosity, high stability, and excellent adsorption capacity at low temperatures. [33,34] Thus, in
129 2012, Alfonse and McCaffrey patented the utilization of a X zeolite in sodium form as an efficient
130 adsorbent to remove organic chlorides from different refinery products. [35] Similarly, Ma et al.
131 investigated the utilization of a Na-X zeolite for the elimination of 5-chloro-2-methylaniline from
132 a model jet fuel [33] while Ge et al. evaluated the incorporation of different transition metals
133 (Ce, Co, Cu, and Ni) over a Na-Y zeolite in the adsorptive dechlorination of a reformat fraction.
134 [36] More recently, Zhang et al. reported the use of Zn-modified H β Zeolites in the removal of
135 different model organochlorinated species from a synthetic naphtha. [37] These investigations
136 have demonstrated the effectiveness of adsorptive dechlorination and its potential to improve
137 the quality of final products and reduce environmental impacts. However, while adsorptive
138 dechlorination has been studied for refinery streams, its specific application for plastic
139 dechlorinating pyrolysis oils has not been explored.

140 In this context, this paper focuses on the dechlorination of a real plastic pyrolysis oil, using
141 commercial FAU and LTA-based zeolites (13X, 4A, and Y) as chlorine adsorbents using mild
142 operating temperatures (< 180 °C). The influence of the zeolite dehydration, temperature, and
143 time on stream (TOS) on the chlorine adsorption was assessed and related to the
144 physicochemical properties of the adsorbent. Among the zeolites tested, the best dechlorination
145 efficiency was attained over dehydrated 13X zeolite, which allowed to obtain an upgraded
146 pyrolysis oil with low chlorine concentration. The regeneration and reusability of this material
147 were also investigated.

148 **2. Experimental Section**

149 *2.1. Zeolite characterization*

150 Three zeolites in sodium form (13X, 4A, and Y), supplied by SILKEM, were used as chlorine
151 adsorbents in this work.

152 The structure and crystallinity of the raw zeolites were assessed by X-ray powder diffraction
153 (XRD) on a Philips PW 3040/00 X'Pert MPD/MRD diffractometer, using CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.154$
154 nm) operated at 45 kV potential and 40 mA intensity. The textural properties of the zeolites

155 were determined from argon adsorption-desorption isotherms at -186 °C, using a Micromeritics
156 3Flex instrument. Before the measurements, the samples (ca. 0.1 g) were degassed at 300 °C for
157 6 h under ultra-high vacuum (10^{-6} mbar). The specific surface area was estimated using the
158 Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) equation, while the total pore volume was calculated at a relative
159 pressure of 0.97. Due to its ultrasmall pore size, the textural properties of zeolite 4A were also
160 analyzed by CO₂ adsorption at 0 °C using the same analyzer and preparation conditions as in the
161 former samples.

162 The morphology of the zeolite particles was investigated by Field Emission Scanning Electron
163 Microscopy (FE-SEM) using a JEOL JSM-7900 microscope operating at 1.0 – 2.0 Kv and equipped
164 with both Lower Electron (LED) and Upper Electron (UED) detectors. The aluminum and sodium
165 contents of the zeolite samples were determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical
166 Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) using a Perkin Elmer Optima 7300AD instrument after acidic
167 digestion with a mixture of nitric and hydrofluoric acids in an Anton Paar Multi-wave 3000
168 microwave.

169 On the other hand, the overall acidity of the zeolites was measured by ammonia temperature
170 programmed desorption (NH₃-TPD) in a Micromeritics AUTOCHEM 2910 apparatus equipped
171 with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). Previously to the analyses, ca. 0.1 g of sample was
172 introduced in a quartz U-tube and pre-treated under a He flow at 600 °C for 60 min. After cooling
173 to 100 °C, the sample was exposed to a 10 %vol. NH₃/He gas mixture. Then, the physisorbed
174 ammonia was removed by flowing He at 100 °C for 30 min. Finally, the chemically adsorbed
175 ammonia was determined by increasing the temperature up to 550 °C with a heating rate of 10
176 °C/min.

177 The contents of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites (BAS and LAS, respectively) were quantified by
178 pyridine desorption, followed by Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy. The samples
179 were prepared as self-supporting wafers ($\varnothing = 13$ mm, 8 – 15 mg/cm²), dried overnight at 120 °C
180 and activated at 500 °C for 2 h under vacuum before adsorbing the probe molecule (pyridine) at
181 150 °C and a pressure of 4 mbar. The spectra were recorded with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ in the
182 4000 – 1000 cm⁻¹ range using a Jasco FT/IR-4600 equipped with a triglycine sulfate (TGS)
183 detector (background, 64 scans; samples, 32 scans). The quantification of both BAS and LAS was
184 performed by integration of the signals detected in the range of 1565–1545 cm⁻¹ for BAS and
185 14545–1544 cm⁻¹ for LAS, using the *Spectra Analysis* software provided by Jasco. The molar
186 extinction coefficients employed were taken from Zholobenko et al., being $\epsilon_{\text{BAS}} = 1.54$ and $\epsilon_{\text{LAS}} =$
187 1.71 cm/ μmol , respectively. [38]

188 Moisture and organic content of the fresh and spent samples were determined by
189 thermogravimetric analysis using a TA Instruments SDT Q600 thermobalance where ca. 15 mg
190 of sample were heated at a rate of 10 °C/min up to 900 °C under a constant air flow of 100
191 ml/min.

192 2.2. Raw Plastic pyrolysis oil characterization

193 The plastic pyrolysis oil used as feedstock in this study, supplied by Repsol (Spain), was obtained
194 from a pyrolysis process of discarded plastics from a municipal solid waste stream. This fraction
195 was mainly composed of polyolefin polymers, low-density polyethylene (LDPE), high-density
196 polyethylene (HDPE), and polypropylene (PP) and with some traces of polyvinyl chloride (PVC),
197 polystyrene (PS), polyethylene terephthalate (PET).

198 The physicochemical properties of the raw pyrolysis oil were determined using various standard
199 methods. Density was determined at 15 °C according to ASTM D4052 procedure using an ISL
200 VIDA 40 automatic densimeter. [39] Viscosity was estimated at 40 °C using a CANNON automatic
201 viscometer (CAV 2100 series) following the ASTM D445 method. [40] The total acid number (mg
202 KOH/g) was measured according to ASTM D664 using a Mettler Toledo potentiometric titrator
203 equipped with a thermometric sensor (Thermotrode). [41] The water content was calculated
204 according to ASTM D6304 using a Mettler Toledo C30S KF coulometric titrator. [42]

205 The total chlorine concentration in the raw pyrolysis oil was determined according to the EPA
206 Standard Method 5050 [43] in an oxygen bomb calorimeter using a trapping solution prepared
207 by mixing 50 ml of a stock solution (0.1 M Na₂CO₃ and 0.2 M NaHCO₃), 25 ml of H₂O₂ (30 wt%)
208 and 7 – 8 lentils of NaOH dissolved in 1 l of Milli-Q water. For this analysis, approximately 0.5 g
209 of pyrolysis oil was combusted under 30 bar of oxygen in the bomb calorimeter, in which 10 ml
210 of the trapping solution was placed. After that, the bomb was cooled down for 10 min and
211 thoroughly rinsed with 90 ml of Milli-Q water to recover the trapping solution containing the
212 absorbed combusted gases. Finally, the resulting chlorinated liquid fraction was analyzed
213 following the EPA Standard Method 9056 [44] in a Metrohm 850 Professional Ionic
214 Chromatograph operated with a Metrosep A Supp 7150/4.0 column and equipped with a Supp
215 5 Guard/4.0 pre-column and a PCC 2 HC/4.0 pre-concentrator column. The total chlorine
216 concentration in the oil was calculated according to equation [1]:

$$217 \quad C_0 = \frac{C_{oil} \cdot V_{oil} \cdot DF}{W_0} \quad [1]$$

218 where C_0 is the initial concentration of chlorine in the sample ($\mu\text{g/g}$), C_{oil} is the concentration of
219 chlorine in the pyrolysis oil ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), measured by ionic-chromatography, V_{oil} is the total volume

220 of combustate (10 ml), DF is the dilution factor (10), and W_0 is the weight of sample combusted
221 (g).

222 Additionally, to determine the boiling point distribution of the different chlorinated compounds
223 present in the feedstock, 20 l of plastic pyrolysis oil were fractionated using a PILODIST 100 CC
224 batch distillation system. The chlorine distribution in the distilled fractions was assessed using
225 the combustion ion chromatography method following the ASTM D7359 standard procedure.
226 [45] Briefly, solution samples were combusted under oxygen-rich pyrohydrolytic conditions. The
227 resulting gaseous HCl was then trapped in an H_2O_2 absorption solution (1000 ppm). The chloride
228 content of this solution was then measured in a 930 Compact Flex ion chromatograph from
229 Metrohm having a polyvinyl alcoholic with quaternary ammonium groups column (Metrosep A
230 Supp 7–150/4.0) as stationary phase and using a sodium carbonate solution as eluent.

231 *2.3. Experimental setup for the dechlorination tests*

232 The pyrolysis oil dechlorination experiments were carried out in a stainless-steel downdraft
233 fixed-bed (Microactivity-Reference, PID Eng & Tech, 9 mm i.d. and 305 mm length) divided into
234 two zones, physically separated by an internal grid, and equipped with a liquid-gas separator
235 (Figure 1). Before being used in the dechlorination assays, the zeolites were pelletized, crushed,
236 and sieved into 0.5 – 1 mm particles. Before each run, the pelletized zeolite was charged into
237 the reactor and the empty space was filled with silicon carbide to avoid preferential paths of the
238 oil when passing through the adsorbent.

239 For each dechlorination assay, 100 ml of oil were continuously fed into the reaction system using
240 an HPLC pump (GILSON 307) at a flow rate of 25 ml/h. The pyrolysis oil passed through a 5 ml
241 adsorbent bed using a liquid hourly space velocity (LHSV) of 5 h^{-1} . The experiments were carried
242 out under an inert atmosphere (1 bar) using nitrogen as carrier gas (10 Nml/min) at
243 temperatures ranging from 30 to 180 °C. The liquid and gaseous phases generated were
244 collected using a Peltier condenser placed at the reactor outlet. To evaluate the effect of zeolite
245 dehydration, additional chlorine removal experiments were performed carrying out an in situ
246 pre-drying step of the zeolite, heating the reactor at 150 °C for 1 h.

247

248 **Figure 1. Lab-scale set-up used for the adsorption assays provided with an adsorbent fixed**
 249 **bed.**

250

251 *2.4. Analysis of the products*

252 The chlorine content of the liquid product was determined according to the EPA Standard
 253 Methods 5050 and 9056 above described [43, 44]. The dechlorination efficiency of each zeolite
 254 was evaluated according to equation [2]:

255
$$\text{Dechlorination efficiency (\%)} = 100 \cdot [(Cl_{in} - Cl_{out}) / Cl_{in}] \quad [2]$$

256 where Cl_{in} and Cl_{out} are, respectively, the inlet and outlet chlorine concentrations in the pyrolysis
 257 oil (ppm).

258 The simulated distillation curve of the dechlorinated pyrolysis oils obtained at different
 259 temperatures was determined following the ASTM D2887 standard method [46] using a Bruker
 260 436-GC SimDist gas chromatograph equipped with a non-polar metallic capillary column CP-
 261 SimDist UltiMetal (10 m × 0.53 mm × 0.53 μm) and a FID detector.

262 *2.5. Adsorbent regeneration process*

263 The regeneration of the spent dehydrated 13X zeolite after the adsorption process at 180 °C was
 264 also investigated. For that purpose, different regeneration procedures were assessed in this
 265 work: a) thermal desorption at 500 °C in a tubular furnace (Carbolite STF 15/450) under a N_2
 266 flow of 100 NmL/min and a heating rate of 10 °C/min, and b) combustion with air at

267 temperatures of 450 and 600 °C in a static muffle oven (Carbolite CWF 1100) with a heating rate
268 of 10 °C/min.

269 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

270 3.1. Properties of the zeolite adsorbents

271 Three Na-zeolites (4A, 13X, and Y) were evaluated in this work as chlorine removal adsorbents
272 from plastic pyrolysis oil. Firstly, the physicochemical properties of these zeolitic materials are
273 discussed in this section.

274 The XRD patterns of these samples (Figure 2a) indicate that the zeolites exhibit a high degree of
275 crystallinity, showing the typical diffraction signals corresponding to the FAU-topology for 13X
276 and Y zeolites and LTA structure in the case of 4A zeolite. [47]

277

285

295 **Figure 2.** XRD patterns (a) and thermogravimetric analyses (analysis conditions: 100 ml/min Air;
296 heating rate, 10 °C/min, from room temperature to 900 °C) (b) of 4A, 13X, and Y zeolites.

297 The Al and Na contents of the zeolites were determined by ICP-OES analyses (Table 1). Both 13X
 298 and 4A samples have similar $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}$ and $[\text{Si}/\text{Na}]_{\text{MOL}}$ ratios with values of 2.1 – 2.2 and 1.9,
 299 respectively. Y zeolite, on the other hand, exhibits slightly lower Al and Na contents with
 300 $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}$ and $[\text{Si}/\text{Na}]_{\text{MOL}}$ ratios of 3.1 and 2.8, respectively.

301 Moisture contents of these samples were calculated from thermogravimetric analyses under air
 302 flow (Figure 2b). All zeolites exhibit a significant weight loss produced at temperatures lower
 303 than 200 °C, typically assigned to physically adsorbed water (Table 1), denoting the high
 304 hydration capacity of these materials due to their high Al and Na contents. [48] In the case of
 305 the 13X and Y zeolites, this signal is accompanied by a shoulder that extends up to 350 °C,
 306 denoting the presence of a small amount of water molecules with a stronger interaction with
 307 the zeolite surface. For Y zeolite, both signals are shifted to lower temperatures, which may be
 308 related to the lower Al content of this sample. In contrast, the 4A sample shows a clear signal
 309 centered at 350 °C, suggesting that water molecules are retained more strongly due to the more
 310 confined space of its zeolitic structure.

311 **Table 1.** Chemical composition and physicochemical properties of the zeolites (textural
 312 properties determined by Ar adsorption at -186 °C in the case of 13X and Y zeolites and by CO₂
 313 adsorption at 0 °C for 4A zeolite).

Adsorbent	$[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}^{\text{a}}$	$[\text{Si}/\text{Na}]_{\text{MOL}}^{\text{a}}$	$S_{\text{BET}}^{\text{b}}$ (m ² /g)	$S_{\text{MIC}}^{\text{c}}$ (m ² /g)	$S_{\text{EXT}}^{\text{c}}$ (m ² /g)	V_{P}^{d} (cm ³ /g)	Moisture ^e (wt%)
4A	2.2	1.9	423	nd	nd	0.237	25.0
13X	2.1	1.9	792	747	45	0.314	28.0
Y	3.1	2.8	870	798	72	0.355	29.8

314 ^a Determined by ICP-OES measurements.

315 ^b Estimated by BET method.

316 ^c Micropore (S_{MIC}) and external surface (S_{EXT}) areas estimated by applying the t-plot method.

317 ^d Total pore volume (V_{P}) calculated at $P/P_0 \approx 0.97$ from Ar isotherms and at $P/P_0 \approx 0.034$ from CO₂
 318 isotherms.

319 ^e Calculated from air-TG analyses.

320

321 Figure 3a shows the Ar physisorption analyses at -186 °C corresponding to 13X and Y zeolites
 322 while Table 1 summarizes the textural parameters of these samples. As observed, 13X and Y
 323 zeolites exhibit a type I isotherm (according to the IUPAC classification), typical of pure
 324 microporous materials. Accordingly, the specific surface areas of these samples, with values of
 325 792 and 870 m²/g, respectively, are mainly related to the zeolitic microporous system ($S_{\text{MIC}}=747$
 326 and 804 m²/g), with a relatively low contribution of the external surface area. In the case of 4A
 327 zeolite, the BET surface area value derived from the Ar isotherm was 27.5 m²/g, which is
 328 significantly lower than the one that would be expected from its crystalline structure. This

329 discrepancy has been earlier attributed to the low diffusion rate of the Ar molecules at cryogenic
 330 temperatures within the ultramicropores of the LTA structure, characterized by sizes smaller
 331 than 4 Å. [49] To overcome this limitation, the textural parameters of this zeolite were also
 332 evaluated by CO₂ physisorption at 0 °C (Figure 3b and Table 1) [50], obtaining a specific surface
 333 area of 423 m²/g, which is more consistent with the crystalline framework of this zeolite.
 334 Compared to the 13X and Y zeolite materials, the BET surface area and the pore volume of the
 335 4A zeolite sample are significantly smaller due to the reduced pore size and the absence of large
 336 voids in the LTA structure.

337

338 **Figure 3.** Adsorption–desorption isotherms: a) of 13X and Y zeolites (Ar at -186 °C); b) 4A zeolite
 339 (CO₂ at 0 °C).

340 The acid properties of the zeolite adsorbents were investigated by NH₃-TPD. The resultant
 341 desorption profiles are displayed in Figure 4, along with the overall acidity values. As observed,
 342 both 4A and 13X zeolites show a very intense signal centered around 200 – 230 °C, which can be
 343 related to the presence of acid sites with moderate strength. [51] In the desorption profile of
 344 13X zeolite, two maximums (172 and 228 °C) are intuited, suggesting that this sample possesses
 345 acid centers of different strengths. No desorption is observed at higher temperatures, which
 346 can be associated with the presence of exchanged Na⁺ cations in the zeolite structure. [52] Due
 347 to their high Al and Na contents, these samples exhibit the greatest overall acidity values (1 and
 348 1.20 mmol/g, respectively). In contrast, zeolite Y displays a less pronounced signal in its
 349 desorption profile, resulting in a lower overall acidity value (0.55 mmol/g), assigned to its lower
 350 Al and Na contents. This curve shows a maximum at around 166 °C suggesting that the acid sites
 351 of this sample possess weaker strength than those of 4A and 13X zeolites.

352 Figure 5 depicts different SEM images of the zeolites here studied. As observed, some
 353 differences can be found in the morphology of FAU and LTA-type zeolites. Hence, 4A zeolite

354 consists of cubic particles around $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ in size, while FAU zeolites crystals (13X and Y zeolites)
355 show a more irregular shape. Some differences can be also found in the size of the zeolitic
356 crystals. Thus, both 4A and 13X zeolites present crystals of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$, while Y zeolitic sample is
357 formed by smaller crystals with a particle size ranging from 0.2 to 0.6 μm , which agrees well with
358 the greater contribution of the external surface of this sample in comparison to the other two
359 microporous zeolites (4A and 13X).

360

361 **Figure 4.** NH_3 -TPD curves for 4A, 13X, and Y zeolites.

362

363

364 **Figure 5.** SEM images of 4A, 13X, and Y zeolites.

365

366 *3.2. Plastic pyrolysis oil composition and properties*

367 Table 2 summarizes the physicochemical properties of the raw pyrolysis oil obtained from real
368 plastic residues used as feedstock in this study. This plastic pyrolysis oil has a density of 0.79
369 g/cm³ at 15 °C and a kinematic viscosity of 1.8 cSt at 40 °C, values which are in the typical range
370 of naphtha and kerosene petrol fractions. [53] However, the total acid number of the oil is 0.83
371 mg KOH/g, much higher than that of naphtha, kerosene, and diesel, which are usually < 0.1 mg
372 KOH/g. [54] This fact can be related to the presence of oxygenated and chlorinated species in
373 the oil. [55] The concentration of chlorine in the pyrolysis oil is very high (421 ppm), hindering
374 its co-processing in conventional refineries, since its presence can cause corrosion and fouling
375 problems, as well as catalyst poisoning in downstream units, requiring a specific treatment to
376 reduce its content.

377 **Table 2.** Raw plastic pyrolysis oil properties.

Property	Value	Test method
Density, 15 °C (kg/l)	0.79	ASTM D4052
Viscosity, 40 °C (cSt)	1.8	ASTM D445
Total acid number (mg KOH/g)	0.8	ASTM D664
Water content (ppm)	53	ASTM D6304
Total chlorine content (ppm)	421	EPA Method 5050 & 9056
Metal content (ppm)		ICP-OES
	Si	39.0
	Fe	3.0
	Others	<1
Distillation curve (°C)		ASTM D2887
	Initial boiling point	38.1
	10 wt%	97.1
	50 wt%	248.3
	90 wt%	367.4
	Final boiling point	433.5

378

379 The pyrolysis oil used as feedstock in this work was fractionated as described in the experimental
380 section. According to the distillation curve (Table 2), most of the components of the oil distillates
381 in the range of 97 – 367.4 °C. This interval includes the average boiling point of naphtha (IBP <
382 150 °C), kerosene (IBP ~150 – 275 °C) and diesel fractions (IBP ~ 200 – 350 °C). The different
383 distillate fractions so obtained were analyzed following the ASTM D7359 standard procedure to
384 determine their chlorine content and, thus, to establish the boiling point distribution of the
385 organochlorinated compounds present in the oil (Figure 6). As observed, 78 wt% of total chlorine

386 compounds is concentrated in the lightest fraction of the pyrolysis oil, with an average boiling
387 point lower than 100 °C whilst 94.4 wt% of total chlorine derivatives is recovered before reaching
388 a boiling temperature of 207 °C. These results indicate that most of the chlorinated compounds
389 contained in the pyrolysis oil are of low molecular weight.

390

391

392 Figure 6. Chlorine distribution in the raw plastic pyrolysis oil according to the distillation curve.

393

394 3.3. Chlorine retention efficiency of the zeolites

395 As previously discussed from TG/DTA analyses, the zeolites investigated as chlorine adsorbents
396 in this work exhibit a high affinity for the adsorption of water. Specifically, 4A, 13X, and Y zeolites
397 showed high moisture contents with values ranging from 25 to 30 wt% (Table 1). To evaluate
398 how the presence of moisture could affect the chlorine retention capacity of the zeolites,
399 different chlorine adsorption tests were performed over both fresh and dehydrated samples.
400 For that, an in situ pre-drying step was carried out at 150 °C for 1 h under an inert atmosphere
401 before the adsorption assays. Subsequently, the chlorine retention efficiency of the zeolites was
402 evaluated at adsorption temperatures of 30 and 120 °C. The results so obtained are presented
403 in Figure 7.

404 The dechlorination efficiency over the fresh zeolites, when working at 30 °C, ranges from 13 to
405 15 %, with no significant differences observed regarding their textural properties and chemical
406 composition. However, when the zeolite samples are subjected to a pre-drying step, the chlorine
407 removal efficiencies are significantly improved in all cases, increasing from about 15 % to a range
408 of 22 to 35.6 % in the adsorption tests conducted at 30 °C, and from 39.4 to 66.4 % when

409 operating at 120 °C. These improvements clearly demonstrate that the presence of physically
410 adsorbed water strongly hinders the chlorine removal ability of the zeolites. It can be envisaged
411 that the adsorbed water molecules are located in the vicinity of the Al/Na sites, thus blocking
412 them towards the adsorption of Cl-containing species.

413

414 **Figure 7.** Effect of the pre-drying step and adsorption temperature on the chlorine retention
415 capacity of the zeolites (LHSV = 5 h⁻¹).

416

417 The dehydrated materials exhibit substantial differences in the chlorine elimination capacity
418 depending on their physicochemical properties as well as the temperature of the Cl adsorption
419 tests. At 30 °C, 4A zeolite shows the lowest chlorine retention efficiency due to the restricted
420 access of the organochloride molecules into the ultrasmall zeolitic micropores of the LTA
421 topology (~4 Å). In all cases, the dechlorination efficiency improves considerably with
422 temperature, denoting that chlorine removal is primarily governed by its chemical adsorption
423 over the Al/Na sites. In this sense, the dehydrated 13X-type zeolite exhibits the best chlorine
424 elimination efficiency, which can be associated with its high content of Al/Na and its accessible
425 zeolitic structure for the Cl-containing species present in the pyrolysis oil. Therefore, this sample
426 was selected for further studies to investigate the effect of temperature and time on stream
427 (TOS).

428 *3.4. Influence of temperature and time on stream (TOS) on the chlorine adsorption efficiency* 429 *of 13X zeolite.*

430 The influence of the operating temperature on the chlorine retention efficiency is first discussed
431 in this section. A series of adsorption tests were conducted using a dehydrated 13X zeolite

432 adsorbent bed operating at temperatures ranging from 30 to 180 °C and a LHSV of 5 h⁻¹. It is
433 important to note that the use of moderate operating temperatures prevents the
434 polymerization of diolefins present in the pyrolysis oil, which could lead to clogging phenomena
435 in pipelines and other refinery equipment.

436 As shown in Figure 8a, the chlorine retention capacity of the dehydrated 13X zeolite is strongly
437 influenced by temperature. The efficiency of chlorine removal gradually increases from 35.6 %
438 at 30 °C to 88 % at 150 °C. Beyond 150 °C, the dechlorination efficiency remains relatively
439 constant, with only a slight increase of 1.2 % at 180 °C. These findings support the previous
440 observations regarding the positive impact of temperature on the chemisorption of Cl-
441 containing species using an aluminum-rich zeolite bed.

442 Moreover, it is also expected that higher temperatures will contribute to preventing the possible
443 adsorption of water present in the raw pyrolysis oil (53 ppm, Table 2). As discussed above, the
444 physisorption of water molecules has a detrimental impact on the chlorine retention capacity of
445 the zeolite. Thus, at low temperatures, water molecules contained in the pyrolysis oil, which
446 exhibit a high affinity with the zeolite, are easily physisorbed on the zeolite surface, inhibiting
447 the chemisorption of the chlorinated species. However, when the temperature increases, the
448 physical adsorption of water is less favored, allowing the zeolite to more effectively retain the
449 organochlorinated species.

450 Table S1 collects the ASTM distillation curves of the pyrolysis oil subjected to dechlorination
451 tests at different temperatures along with that of the raw pyrolysis oil. As observed, the boiling
452 point distribution of the dechlorinated pyrolysis oils is quite similar to that of the raw oil. This
453 suggests that, within the temperature range evaluated in this study, the cooling system placed
454 at the reactor outlet efficiently condenses the pyrolysis oil. Moreover, it can be concluded that
455 no significant cracking reactions, which could reduce the average molecular weight or
456 hydrocarbon length of the oil components, take place during the adsorption tests. In the same
457 way, the absence of any mass loss in the form of coke or non-condensable gases further supports
458 the idea that the dechlorination process using a 13X zeolite bed does not promote any
459 undesirable side reaction that could alter the composition of the pyrolysis oil. Thus, the zeolite
460 adsorbent seems to specifically target the chlorinated compounds in the oil without affecting its
461 composition.

462 Overall, these findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the dechlorination process at different
463 temperatures using a 13X zeolite bed, as it efficiently removes chlorine without causing
464 significant changes in the boiling point distribution or composition of the pyrolysis oil.

465

466

467 **Figure 8.** Adsorption temperature study for the dehydrated 13X zeolite: a) dechlorination
 468 efficiency and b) outlet chlorine concentration and ASTM distillation curve of the raw plastic
 469 pyrolysis oil (ASTM D-2887). [46]

470

471 To study the evolution of the chlorine concentration overtime during the dechlorination process,
 472 several aliquots of the dechlorinated oils were collected and analyzed at different times on
 473 stream. These assays were performed at temperatures of 30 and 180 °C using the dehydrated
 474 13X zeolite as an adsorbent (Figure 9a). From these data, both dechlorination efficiency as well
 475 as the amount of adsorbed chlorine (in terms of mmol per gram) of zeolite were also calculated
 476 (Figures 9b and c). As above discussed, the chlorine removal efficiency was favored at higher
 477 temperatures, the outlet chlorine concentration in the pyrolysis oil being much lower at 180 °C
 478 than that obtained at 30 °C.

479 At the lowest temperatures (30 °C), a rapid decrease in the chlorine outlet concentration is
 480 observed during the first 30 minutes of the time on stream. Consequently, the chlorine removal
 481 efficiency drops from approximately 77-82 % to around 45 % after 1 h of testing. In contrast, at

482 180 °C, the chlorine outlet concentration remains relatively stable at around 25-30 ppm for at
483 least 3 h of time on stream. Subsequently, the chlorine concentration undergoes a progressive
484 increase, reaching a value of 230 ppm after 6 h of testing. This gradual decline of the
485 dechlorination efficiency denotes that the adsorbent becomes progressively saturated over
486 time. Nevertheless, after 6 h of testing, the amount of chlorine retained in the zeolitic adsorbent
487 was more than double at 180 °C (0.32 mmol of Cl/g of zeolite) compared to that achieved at 30
488 °C (0.14 mmol of Cl/g of zeolite). Two complementary effects could be proposed to explain this
489 finding: a) the lower retention of water by the adsorbent as the temperature increases and b)
490 the shift from liquid to vapor phase adsorption of the organochlorinated species, which implies
491 a quite faster diffusion of the latter. This result highlights the advantage of operating at higher
492 temperatures for the adsorptive dechlorination process, as it leads to a substantial increase in
493 the chlorine retention capacity of the zeolite adsorbent.

494

495

496

497 **Figure 9.** Evolution with time on stream: a) outlet chlorine concentration; b) dechlorination
 498 efficiency; and c) adsorbed chlorine per gram of zeolite.

499

500 3.5. Adsorbent regeneration process

501 To address the adsorbent reusability, three regeneration processes are investigated in this
 502 section: a) thermal desorption under an inert atmosphere at 500 °C; b) air combustion at 450
 503 °C; and c) air combustion at 600 °C. These regeneration treatments were applied to the spent
 504 dehydrated 13X zeolite after a Cl adsorption test at 180 °C for 4 h.

505 Figure 10 compares the dechlorination efficiency evolution along the time on stream for the
506 fresh zeolite and the samples subjected to the different regeneration treatments. Initially, the
507 chlorine retention capacity of the fresh zeolite slightly decreases from 93 % at 1 h of time on
508 stream to 78 % after 4 h of the adsorption test. When subjected to a thermal desorption at 500
509 °C, the adsorbent shows a dechlorination efficiency of 79 % after 1 h of testing, which then
510 linearly decreases to 43 % during the subsequent 4 h of the adsorption test. The regeneration
511 by combustion at 450 °C results in a recovery of a dechlorination efficiency of up to 91 % after 1
512 h of the assay. However, this value rapidly decreases to 45 % by the end of the experiment. The
513 limited effectiveness of these treatments can be explained by considering the TG/DTG profiles
514 of these zeolites (Figure 11). Thus, the DTG curves of these samples exhibit two peaks: one
515 around 150 – 180 °C, related to the removal of physically adsorbed water molecules, and, a
516 second signal, in the range of 380 – 400 °C, suggesting the presence of organic matter in the
517 zeolite. These findings reveal that the previous thermal treatments are insufficient to remove
518 the organic compounds occluded in the zeolitic micropores. For that reason, a more severe air
519 combustion treatment at 600 °C was subsequently assessed for the regeneration of the zeolite.
520 In this case, the regenerated zeolite exhibits a similar chlorine retention capacity to that of the
521 fresh zeolite after the first 3 h of time on stream. Consequently, the thermogram of this sample
522 closely resembles that of the fresh zeolite, showing a significant weight loss at temperatures
523 lower than 350 °C, which was previously assigned to water desorption. However, there is a more
524 pronounced decrease in the dechlorination efficiency in the last hour of the assay.

525 The textural properties of the regenerated 13X zeolite through air combustion at 600 °C were
526 determined and compared to the fresh sample (Table 3). As observed, the BET surface area and
527 total pore volume are somewhat reduced after the regeneration treatment. In addition, the acid
528 properties of both fresh and regenerated adsorbents were evaluated by Pyr-FTIR. The resulting
529 spectra after desorption at 150 °C are shown in Fig. S1, while the concentrations of Bronsted
530 and Lewis acid sites are collected in Table 3. In the FT-IR spectra, no band can be detected
531 around 1545 cm⁻¹ and 1637 cm⁻¹, which are the wavenumber values of the signals typically
532 associated with pyridinium cations (PyH⁺) chemisorbed on BAS. This fact indicates that both
533 fresh and regenerated zeolites have an almost negligible amount of BAS, which is consistent
534 with the presence of Na⁺ as a counterion. Accordingly, the main signals appearing in the spectra
535 of both samples are those related to the presence of LAS. According to the previous studies, the
536 bands located at 1590 cm⁻¹ and 1454-1440 cm⁻¹ are assigned to molecular pyridine adsorbed on
537 weakly Lewis acidic Na⁺ cations. On the other hand, the signal at 1613 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to
538 stronger Lewis acid site related to very highly exposed Na⁺ ions, or Al³⁺ ions. [56,57] Thus, it has

539 been reported that the Lewis acidity of the Na⁺ cations is a very relevant feature for the practical
540 application of Na-zeolites, which are known to be very effective adsorbents for a variety of
541 species like water, CO, H₂S, ammonia and nitriles. [56] Consequently, a similar effect can be
542 envisaged in the current work to establish a relationship between the presence of a significant
543 concentration of LAS in the 13X zeolite sample and the dechlorination efficiency of this material,
544 those centers acting as adsorption sites of the organochlorinated species.

545 Despite the observed small decrease in the dechlorination efficiency, it can be concluded that
546 the regeneration of the zeolite by air combustion at 600 °C is an effective procedure for
547 recovering most of its chlorine adsorption capacity. This is a very promising result since it
548 demonstrates that the spent 13 X zeolite can be successfully regenerated and reused, making it
549 a more sustainable and cost-effective option for dechlorination applications.

550

551

552 **Figure 10.** Dechlorination curves of the adsorption process at 180 °C for the dehydrated 13X
553 zeolite, fresh and after different regeneration procedures.

554

555 **Figure 11.** TGA and DTG curves of fresh and regenerated 13X zeolites. Matter content is
 556 expressed as 100 gram of weight loss of the initial weight per gram of dried zeolite.

557 **Table 3.** Comparison between fresh and regenerated 13X zeolite by air combustion at 600 °C.

Adsorbent	S_{BET} (m^2/g) ^a	S_{EXT} (m^2/g) ^b	S_{MIC} (m^2/g) ^b	V_{P} (cm^3/g) ^c	Brønsted acid sites, 150 °C (mmol g^{-1}) ^d	Lewis acid sites, 150 °C (mmol g^{-1}) ^d
Fresh 13X	792	45	747	0.314	0.001	0.889
Reg. Combustion 600 °C	744	49	695	0.307	0.001	0.815

558 ^a Estimated by BET method.

559 ^b Micropore (S_{MIC}) and external surface (S_{EXT}) areas estimated by applying the t-plot method.

560 ^c Total pore volume (V_{P}) calculated at $P/P_0 \approx 0.97$ from Ar isotherms.

561 ^d FTIR spectroscopy of pyridine adsorption analyses.

562

563

564

4. CONCLUSIONS

565 Three commercial zeolites, 4A, 13X, and Y (in sodium form), were investigated as adsorbents for
 566 the dechlorination of a real plastic pyrolysis oil in a fixed bed set-up. Initially, these zeolites
 567 showed moderate chlorine removal efficiencies when they were tested as-received state.
 568 However, their performance was significantly improved by conducting an in situ pre-drying step
 569 at 150 °C before the adsorption process, which indicates that the presence of physisorbed water
 570 molecules has an inhibiting effect on the chlorine retention capacity of the zeolites. 13X zeolite
 571 led to the best dechlorination efficiencies, which is attributed to its high Lewis acid sites
 572 concentration, due to the presence of Na^+ ionically interacting with the zeolite framework and
 573 acting as effective adsorption centers for the organochlorinated species. In addition, the
 574 dechlorination performance of the 13X zeolite is also favored by the occurrence of large zeolitic

575 pore sizes and voids, characteristic of the FAU topology, which enhance the accessibility of the
576 organochlorine compounds to the Al/Na adsorption sites.

577 For 13X zeolite, the dechlorination efficiency increased with temperature not producing
578 significant variations in the boiling point distribution of the hydrocarbons present in the pyrolysis
579 oil. However, the chlorine removal ability of the zeolite significantly decreased after 2-3 h of
580 time of stream, this effect being more pronounced at lower temperatures. The Cl elimination
581 efficiency of the zeolite can be recovered by regeneration treatment consisting of an air
582 combustion treatment at 600 °C, achieving removal percentages during the first 3 h of time on
583 stream comparable to those of the fresh sample. In conclusion, this study offers a promising
584 alternative for efficient chlorine removal from plastic pyrolysis oils using sodium zeolites as
585 adsorbents.

586 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

587 The authors thank the financial support of the Community of Madrid through the project
588 reference: IND2018/AMB-9594 (RESUCAP). Silkem are highly acknowledged for supplying the
589 zeolite samples.

590 REFERENCES

- 591 1. S. Kaza, L. Yao, P. Bhada-Tata, F. Van Woerden, What a Waste 2.0: A Global Snapshot of Solid
592 Waste Management to 2050, Urban Development Series (2018) 29.
- 593 2. C. Zhou, W. Fang, W. Xu, A. Cao, R. Wang, Characteristics and the recovery potential of plastic
594 wastes obtained from landfill mining, J Clean Prod 80 (2014) 80–86.
595 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.05.083>.
- 596 3. F. Zhang, Y. Zhao, D. Wang, M. Yan, J. Zhang, P. Zhang, T. Ding, L. Chen, C. Chen, Current
597 technologies for plastic waste treatment: A review, J Clean Prod 282 (2021) 124523.
598 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124523>.
- 599 4. Plastic Europe, Plastics-the Facts 2022, 2022. [https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-](https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-hub/plastics-the-facts-2022)
600 [hub/plastics-the-facts-2022](https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-hub/plastics-the-facts-2022) (accessed December 11, 2023).
- 601 5. W. Leal, U. Saari, M. Fedoruk, A. Iital, H. Moora, An overview of the problems posed by plastic
602 products and the role of extended producer responsibility in Europe, J Clean Prod 214 (2019)
603 550–558. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.256>.
- 604 6. E. Comission, A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy, (2018).

- 605 7. H. Jeswani, C. Krüger, M. Russ, M. Horlacher, F. Antony, S. Hann, A. Azapagic, Life cycle
606 environmental impacts of chemical recycling via pyrolysis of mixed plastic waste in comparison
607 with mechanical recycling and energy recovery, *Sci Total Environ* 769 (2021) 144483.
608 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144483>.
- 609 8. T. Xayachak, N. Haque, R. Parthasarathy, S. King, N. Emami, D. Lau, B.K. Pramanik, Pyrolysis
610 for Plastic Waste Management: An Engineering Perspective, *J Environ Chem Eng* (2022) 108865.
611 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.108865>.
- 612 9. S.M. Al-Salem, A. Antelava, A. Constantinou, G. Manos, A. Dutta, A review on thermal and
613 catalytic pyrolysis of plastic solid waste (PSW), *J Environ Manage* 197 (2007) 177–198.
614 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.03.084>.
- 615 10. R.K. Singh, B. Ruj, Time and temperature depended fuel gas generation from pyrolysis of real
616 world municipal plastic waste, *Fuel* 174 (2016) 164–171.
617 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2016.01.049>.
- 618 11. S.H. Chang, Plastic waste as pyrolysis feedstock for plastic oil production: A review, *Sci Total*
619 *Environ* 877 (2023) 162719. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162719>.
- 620 12. Y. Peng, Y. Wang, L. Ke, L. Dai, Q. Wu, K. Cobb, R. Ruan, A review on catalytic pyrolysis of
621 plastic wastes to high-value products, *Energy Convers Manag* 254 (2022) 115243.
622 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2022.115243>.
- 623 13. P.A. Owusu, N. Banadda, A. Zziwa, J. Seay, N. Kiggundu, Reverse engineering of plastic waste
624 into useful fuel products, *J Anal Appl Pyrolysis* 130 (2018) 285–293.
625 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2017.12.020>.
- 626 14. A. López, I. de Marco, B.M. Caballero, M.F. Laresgoiti, A. Adrados, Pyrolysis of municipal
627 plastic wastes: Influence of raw material composition, *Waste Manage* 30 (2010) 620–627.
628 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2009.10.014>.
- 629 15. A. Adrados, I. De Marco, A. Lopez-Uriónabarrenechea, B.M. Caballero, M.F. Laresgoiti,
630 Pyrolysis behavior of different type of materials contained in the rejects of packaging waste
631 sorting plants, *Waste Manage* 33 (2013) 52–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2012.09.016>.
- 632 16. M. Kusenberg, A. Zayoud, M. Roosen, H. Dao, M.S. Abbas-abadi, A. Eschenbacher, U.
633 Kresovic, S. De Meester, K.M. Van Geem, A comprehensive experimental investigation of plastic

634 waste pyrolysis oil quality and its dependence on the plastic waste composition, Fuel Process
635 Technol 227 (2022) 107090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2021.107090>.

636 17. W. Ma, G. Hoffmann, M. Schirmer, G. Chen, V.S. Rotter, Chlorine characterization and
637 thermal behavior in MSW and RDF, J Hazard Mater 178 (2010) 489–498.
638 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2010.01.108>.

639 18. D. Torres, Y. Jiang, D.A. Sanchez Monsalve, G.A. Leeke, Chlorine removal from the pyrolysis
640 of urban polyolefinic waste in a semi-batch reactor, J Environ Chem Eng 9 (2021) 104929.
641 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.104920>.

642 19. M. Kusenbergl, A. Eschenbacher, M.R. Djokic, A. Zayoud, K. Ragaert, S. De Meester, K.M. Van
643 Geem, Opportunities and challenges for the application of post-consumer plastic waste pyrolysis
644 oils as steam cracker feedstocks: To decontaminate or not to decontaminate?, Waste Manage
645 138 (2022) 83–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2021.11.009>.

646 20. J. Hubáček, J. Lederer, P. Kuráň, P. Koutník, Z. Gholami, M. Zbuzek, M. Bačiak, Dechlorination
647 during pyrolysis of plastics: The potential of stepwise pyrolysis in combination with metal
648 sorbents, Fuel Process Technol 231 (2022) 107226.
649 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2022.107226>.

650 21. H.C. Genuino, M.P. Ruiz, H.J. Heeres, S.R.A. Kersten, Pyrolysis of mixed plastic waste (DKR-
651 350): Effect of washing pre-treatment and fate of chlorine, Fuel Process Technol 233 (2022)
652 107304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2022.107304>.

653 22. S.D. Anuar Sharuddin, F. Abnisa, W.M.A. Wan Daud, M.K. Aroua, A review on pyrolysis of
654 plastic wastes, Energy Convers Manag 115 (2016) 308–326.
655 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2016.02.037>.

656 23. S.M.R. Mirkarimi, S. Bensaid, D. Chiaramonti, Conversion of mixed waste plastic into fuel for
657 diesel engines through pyrolysis process: A review, Appl Energy 327 (2022) 120040.
658 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.120040>.

659 24. A. López, I. De Marco, B.M. Caballero, M.F. Laresgoiti, A. Adrados, Dechlorination of fuels in
660 pyrolysis of PVC containing plastic wastes, in: Fuel Process Technol, 92 (2011) 253–260.
661 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2010.05.008>.

- 662 25. K.B. Park, S.J. Oh, G. Begun, J.S. Kim, Production of clean oil with low levels of chlorine and
663 olefins in a continuous two-stage pyrolysis of a mixture of waste low-density polyethylene and
664 polyvinyl chloride, *Energy* 157 (2018) 402–411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.05.182>.
- 665 26. W. Kaminsky, J.S. Kim, Pyrolysis of mixed plastics into aromatics, *J Anal Appl Pyrolysis* 51
666 (1999) 127–134. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-2370\(99\)00012-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-2370(99)00012-1).
- 667 27. B. Fekhar, L. Gombor, N. Miskolczi, Pyrolysis of chlorine contaminated municipal plastic
668 waste: In-situ upgrading of pyrolysis oils by Ni/ZSM-5, Ni/SAPO-11, red mud and Ca(OH)₂
669 containing catalysts, *Journal of the Energy Institute* 92 (2019) 1270–1283.
670 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joei.2018.10.007>.
- 671 28. Q. Zhou, W. Lan, A. Du, Y. Wang, J. Yang, Y. Wu, K. Yang, X. Wang, Lanthania promoted MgO:
672 Simultaneous highly efficient catalytic degradation and dehydrochlorination of
673 polypropylene/polyvinyl chloride, *Appl Catal B* 80 (2008) 141–146.
674 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2007.11.018>.
- 675 29. J. Yanik, M.A. Uddin, K. Ikeuchi, Y. Sakata, The catalytic effect of Red Mud on the degradation
676 of poly (vinyl chloride) containing polymer mixture into fuel oil, *Polym Degrad Stab* 73 (2001)
677 335–346. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(01\)00095-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(01)00095-7).
- 678 30. A. Marino, A. Aloise, H. Hernando, J. Feroso, D. Cozza, E. Giglio, M. Migliori, P. Pizarro, G.
679 Giordano, D.P. Serrano, ZSM-5 zeolites performance assessment in catalytic pyrolysis of PVC-
680 containing real WEEE plastic wastes, *Catal Today* 390–391 (2022) 210–220.
681 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2021.11.033>.
- 682 31. M. Kusenbergh, A. Eschenbacher, L. Delva, S. De Meester, E. Delikonstantis, G.D. Stefanidis,
683 K. Ragaert, K.M. Van Geem, Towards high-quality petrochemical feedstocks from mixed plastic
684 packaging waste via advanced recycling: The past, present and future, *Fuel Process Techno* 238
685 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2022.107474>.
- 686 32. A. Lopez-Uriónabarrenechea, I. De Marco, B.M. Caballero, M.F. Laresgoiti, A. Adrados,
687 Upgrading of chlorinated oils coming from pyrolysis of plastic waste, *Fuel Process Techno* 137
688 (2015) 229–239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2015.04.015>.
- 689 33. R. Ma, J. Zhu, B. Wu, X. Li, Adsorptive removal of organic chloride from model jet fuel by Na-
690 LSX zeolite: Kinetic, equilibrium and thermodynamic studies, *Chem Eng Res Des* 114 (2016) 321–
691 330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2016.08.028>.

- 692 34. R.E. Reusser, US Patent 3862900 (1975).
- 693 35. M. Alfonse, R.T. McCaffrey, U.S. Patent. 20120190906 (2012).
- 694 36. X. Ge, L. Shi, X. Wang, Dechlorination of reformat via chemical adsorption reactions by Ce-
695 Y zeolite, Ind Eng Chem Res 53 (2014) 6351–6357. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie500314a>.
- 696 37. N. Zhang, R. Li, G. Zhang, L. Dong, D. Zhang, G. Wang, T. Li, Zn-Modified H β Zeolites Used in
697 the Adsorptive Removal of Organic Chloride from Model Naphtha, ACS Omega 5 (2020) 11987–
698 11997. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.9b04417>.
- 699 38. V. Zholobenko, C. Freitas, M. Jendrlin, P. Bazin, A. Travert, F. Thibault-Starzyk, Probing the
700 acid sites of zeolites with pyridine: Quantitative AGIR measurements of the molar absorption
701 coefficients, J Catal 385 (2020) 52-60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcat.2020.03.003>.
- 702 39. Standard Test for Density and Relative Density of Liquids by Digital Density Meter, ASTM-
703 D4052. ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA.
- 704 40. Standard Test Method for Kinematic Viscosity of Transparent and Opaque Liquids (and
705 Calculation of Dynamic Viscosity), ASTM D445. ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA.
- 706 41. Standard Test Method for Acid Number of Petroleum Products by Potentiometric Titration,
707 ASTM D664. ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA.
- 708 42. Standard Test Method for Determination of Water in Petroleum Products, Lubricating Oils,
709 and Additives by Coulometric Karl Fischer Titration, ASTM D6304. ASTM International, West
710 Conshohocken, PA.
- 711 43. US EPA SW-846. Method 5050. Bomb preparation method for solid waste. United States
712 Environmental Protection Agency.
- 713 44. US EPA SW-846. Method 9056A. Determination of inorganic anions by ion chromatography.
714 United States Environmental Protection Agency.
- 715 45. Standard Test Method for Total Fluorine, Chlorine and Sulfur in Aromatic Hydrocarbons and
716 Their Mixtures by Oxidative Pyrohydrolytic Combustion followed by Ion Chromatography
717 Detection (Combustion Ion Chromatography-CIC), ASTM D7359. ASTM International, West
718 Conshohocken, PA.
- 719 46. Standard Test Method for Boiling Range Distribution of Petroleum Fractions by Gas
720 Chromatography, ASTM D2887. ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA.

- 721 47. J.L. Cerrillo, A.E. Palomares, F. Rey, S. Valencia, L. Palou, Ag-zeolites as fungicidal material:
722 Control of citrus green mold caused by *Penicillium digitatum*, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater*
723 254 (2017) 69–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2017.03.036>.
- 724 48. A.H. Ahmed, M.S. Thabet, Metallo-hydrazone complexes immobilized in zeolite Y: Synthesis,
725 identification and acid violet-1 degradation, *J Mol Struct* 1006 (2011) 52 7–535.
726 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2011.09.061>.
- 727 49. J. García-Martínez, D. Cazorla-Amorós, A. Linares-Solano, Further evidences of the
728 usefulness of CO₂ adsorption to characterize microporous solids, *Stud Surf Sci Catal*, 128 (2000)
729 485-494, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2991\(00\)80054-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2991(00)80054-3).
- 730 50. S.M.P. Lucena, J.C.A. Oliveira, D.V. Gonçalves, L.M.O. Lucas, P.A.S. Moura, R.G. Santiago,
731 D.C.S. Azevedo, Moises Bastos-Neto, LTA Zeolite Characterization Based on Pore Type
732 Distribution, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 61 (2022) 5, 2268–2279.
733 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.1c04897>.
- 734 51. N.R. Bocanegra, J.R. De la Rosa, C.J.L. Ortiz, P.C. González, H.C. Greenwell, V.E.B. Almaráz,
735 D.A.D.H. Del Río, Catalytic conversion of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (5-HMF) over Pd-Ru/FAU
736 zeolite catalysts, *Catal Today* 360 (2021) 2–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2019.11.032>
- 737 52. G. Busca, Acidity and basicity of zeolites: A fundamental approach, *Microporous Mesoporous*
738 *Mater* 254 (2017) 3–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2017.04.007>
- 739 53. F.A. Aisien, E.T. Aisien, Production and characterization of liquid oil from the pyrolysis of
740 waste high-density polyethylene plastics using spent fluid catalytic cracking catalyst, *Sustainable*
741 *Chemistry for Climate Action* (2023) 100020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scca.2023.100020>.
- 742 54. A. Gala, M. Guerrero, B. Guirao, M.E. Domine, J.M. Serra, Characterization and distillation of
743 pyrolysis liquids coming from polyolefins segregated of MSW for their use as automotive diesel
744 fuel, *Energy Fuels* 34 (2020) 5969–5982. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.0c00403>.
- 745 55. W. Zeb, M. Roosen, P. Knockaert, S. Janssens, D. Withoek, M. Kusenberg, J. Hogie, P. Billen,
746 S. Tavernier, K.M. Van Geem, S. De Meester, Purification and characterisation of post-consumer
747 plastic pyrolysis oil fractionated by vacuum distillation, *J Clean Prod* 416 (2023).
748 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137881>.
- 749 56. Guido Busca, Acidity and basicity of zeolites: A fundamental approach, *Micropor Mesopor*
750 *Mater* 254 (2017) 3-16, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2017.04.007>.

751 57. T.K. Phung, M.M. Carnasciali, E.A. Finocchio, G. Busca, Catalytic conversion of ethyl acetate
752 over faujasite zeolites, Appl Catal A-Gen, 470 (2014) 72-80,
753 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcata.2013.10.028>.

754